

ISSN 2587-4713

VOLUME 104.

ISSUE 3-5. 2021

DOI: 10.36962/EC

ტომი 104, 3-5. 2021

ECONOMICS

ეკონომიკა

1918

მეცნიერება, პრაქტიკა, გამოცდილება

SCIENCE, PRACTICE, EXPERIENCE

ISSN 2587-4713 DOI:10.36962/EC

ეკონომიკა
ECONOMICS

ტომი 104, 3-5 2021
VOLUME 104, ISSUE 3-5 2021

ჟურნალი, თითოეული სტატია ინდექსირდება
საერთაშორისო სამეცნიერო ბაზაში „CROSSREF“

JOURNAL INDEXING
CROSSREF

საქართველო, თბილისი 2021
GEORGIA, TBILISI, 2021

ეკონომიკა

ყოველთვიური საერთაშორისო რეცენზირებადი და
რეფერირებადი სამეცნიერო ჟურნალი
„ЭКОНОМИКА“ - Ежемесячный международный
рецензируемый и реферируемый научный журнал
“ECONOMICS” - Monthly International reviewed
and refereed scientific journal

ტომი 104, 3-5. 2021
VOLUME 104, ISSUE 3-5. 2021
DOI:10.36962/EC

ჟურნალი გამოდის 1918 წლიდან
Journal published since 1918

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თბილისი - 2021

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education system, for the improvement of human capital. That should ensure the continuous update of the knowledge obtained at the higher Education institutions in parallel with the scientific and technical progress improved level. All this requires a lot of private initiatives, less regulation by the state and in the right direction of finances, reasonable and targeted spending.

In Summary, the goal of the ongoing education reform is to make education not just as a business but to make it more as a **public good**. Since education is the most significant sphere for accumulation of human capital and dissemination of knowledge in modern *digital economy*, it is necessary to increase the role of the state in improving this field.

Keywords: Human Capital, Investment, Education, Competition.

3. The Peculiarities of Foreign Exchange and Insurance Markets

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RESUME

Foreign exchange risk is one of the most important components of the financial market. Like any other financial risk, it can be managed or avoided. Financial risk management requires the relevant knowledge and resources and only specialized financial institutions are engaged in doing so. Thee commercial banks do not accept foreign exchange risks, their assets and liabilities are denominated in the same currency. Therefore, it is recommended for households and businesses to avoid the currency risk.

People's behavior is different during the sharp fluctuations of exchange rates. There is no ideal tactic for behavior. However, we would like to share some basic tips to help you reduce your expected financial risks; At the same time, the undesirable attitude characteristic of the period of strong fluctuations in the course will become clearer and

more preventive. We hope that the information presented in such circumstances will help you to make the right decision.

Keywords: Foreign exchange and insurance market efficiency; Exchange rate risk insurance; Involvement of financial instruments.

4. Financial and Economic Indicators of Shipping Companies in 2010-2019 Years

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RESUME

Financial and Economic analysis of shipping companies conducted based on main maritime industry segments - Crude Oil, Products, Liquefied Natural Gas (LNG), Dry bulk commodities and Container cargo. Each of them is represented as one or several companies, which are the leaders in these business sectors.

The revenues of shipping companies specialized in crude oil and product transportation have been increased significantly in 2010-2019 years, which was a result of increasing ship quantities and tonnage as well as income from time-charter. Stability can be seen in the revenues of liquefied natural gas shipping companies. The growth rate of container shipping company income was comparatively low.

Publication Requirements for Scientific Articles:

The Journal, also articles are indexed in the international scientific base CROSSREF and are assigned an unique International Digital Object Identifier (DOI). (<http://search.crossrf.org>)

The articles to be published in the journal should include the **new results** of scientific research in the theoretical and other practical fields of economics, such as: Economic reform; Modern problems of economics; History of economic doctrines; Legal Provision of Market Economy; Finances, Banks, Exchange Markets; Regional Economy; Sectoral Economy; Current issues of Business, Marketing, Management; World economy; Reviews on monographs and textbooks published recently.

All received scientific articles will be peer-reviewed by the Editorial Board and will be published in case of positive reviews and assessment. The accepted articles will be posted on the website, in the electronic journal.

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Name, surname, academic degree of the author (authors) in Georgian and English,

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For Georgian text, please use the Georgian font **AcadNusx**.

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სოხუმის სახელმწიფო უნივერსიტეტი

გადაეცა ასაწვობად 15.03.2021 წ.
ხელმოწერილია დასაბეჭდად 03.04.2021 წ.
სააღრიცხვო-საგამომცემლო თაბანი 12,75

ЎЎЎ (UDC): 338(922)(05)

